

TECHNOLOGIZATION OF THE PROCESSES OF PREPARING STUDENTS OF THE FUTURE DIRECTION OF PRIMARY EDUCATION FOR CREATIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *News that people uncover continues to fill the expansion of the universe. The human factor, teaching it, and educating it have remained a social order of the evolution of society regardless of the substance, essence, or designation of the phases of growth in the history of mankind. Because it is regarded as "a harmonious personality - the foundation of society's development". Naturally, it is for a reason that the development of a peaceful generation with an element of autonomous, creative thought is given special attention in our nation and is listed among the tasks that are of the utmost importance. This article provides feedback and feedback on the technologization of the processes of preparing students of the future direction of primary education for creative activity.*

Keywords: *primary education, process, technology, students, direction, activity, training.*

In particular, there are opportunities to train the trainee in the activities of creativity, to form elements of creative thinking in them, as well as to further grow and improve their understanding and imagination in this regard. Psychologist scientist N.D.Levitov proved that creative activity arises on the basis of the following criteria:

- independence of thinking;
- assimilation, speed and strength of educational material;
- when solving non-standard tasks, the speed of mental testing;
- to be able to distinguish the important from the non-essential by penetrating deeply into the essence of the phenomena under study.

By the conditions for the formation of creative activity in students, first of all, the process of emergence, implementation and development of these conditions is understood. They consist of:

Knowledge, skills and abilities that students should acquire in this regard in the formation of their creative activity.

The relationship of practice with theoretical knowledge in the formation of creative activity.

Classes on the formation of creative activity heuristics create problematic situations.

These conditions are implemented as follows. In the formation of the creative activity of students, the following requirements are imposed on the knowledge, qualifications, skills that they must possess:

- to what extent the program has mastered the materials;
- mastery of basic concepts and rules regarding topics;
- ability to independently complete assignments on the chosen topic;
- awareness of the main problems in the studied topics;

ability to use educational items and technical means, information technology when completing assignments;

being able to show his ability and develop it;

be able to set goals to be achieved on the subject, make plans and evaluate the results;

being able to prove one's opinion when studying topics;

be able to recommend its option, etc.

These requirements will assist the teacher in determining the organization of the educational process in this regard as well as the students' learning preferences, educational and cognitive activities, and personal preferences. Priority areas for the focused organization of problem-related education are established based on the aforementioned parameters. A purposeful approach is a system of educational content, methods, and forms that is specifically arranged to foster the growth of creative activity. One of the main tasks of pedagogy is to create conditions that ensure the comprehensive development of the creative activity of students. At the same time, it is necessary to identify students who show their deep interests, aspirations and abilities in certain areas, to provide them with all the opportunities for further development. And for this: it is important to create conditions for the development of creative activity of students. In this regard:

Preparation of students for innovative activities on the development of creative activity.

To establish cooperation activities in the relationship of teachers and students.

The use of innovative technologies regarding cognition in the development of creative activity.

Heuristic and problematic education, which is linked to students' individual search for and discovery of a certain truth, is currently making an active entry into the educational and cognitive process. Heuristics are techniques that I'll look for and find. Heuristic actions should be technologically advanced since it is both ethical and necessary to do so. On the basis of heuristic-oriented activities, a single training session, or systematic training in the training course, takes place. The best technique to guarantee the outcomes of the technical movement's creativity for creation and progress is to use heuristic scenarios. In the paragraphs that follow, we'll think about how technology can help teachers plan for and manage heuristic situations.

The primary educational component of the circumstance is referred to by the seeker (Thing, concept, phenomenon, process, tradition, object, etc.). By doing this, you can find out what interests the students and help them develop an inner connection with the subject matter, which will help them think of ways to tackle problems that are important to them personally. Personal experience and student academic performance are estimated for this. Unknown solutions to problems or assignments are supplied to students. Only when there is an educational promotion in the classroom and students demonstrate their activity by finishing the assignment, is the implementation of this assignment beneficial. The definition of the assignment can be the result of a collective discussion of the problem. Only the goal will be achieved if the task described by the students is not just interesting, but news for the teacher.

To give students the chance to independently resolve a problem (task) they made or encountered. It is regarded as the primary phase of the heuristic scenario. In this situation, it is vital to identify the creative evidence in any educational output. Students' examples of educational creativity are displayed. Tasks, definitions, symbols, drawings, projects, layouts, etc. are discussed in teams. Students also organize exhibitions and give speeches during lectures. After seeing examples of instructional creativity, being able to support claims with illustrations, stories,

definitions, expert opinions, data from textbooks, personal knowledge, and imagination. Organization of activities of students in comparison, comparison, classification of samples of creativity. If there are cases of identification by students of their own views or patterns of creativity, they are assisted in their understanding of the reason for the change in their point of view. The development of educational situations is ensured.

Argumentation, evaluation of pupils' knowledge of applied cognitive methods, the issue at hand and potential solutions. assistance in assessing pupils' accomplishments on an individual basis. determination of academic outcomes developed together. Motivation, posing issues for participants to solve, exhibiting educational findings, and contrasting them are the major technology components of research educational scenarios. The instructor sets up the learning environment in the following manner: the necessary materials and educational objects are identified, their relationships are examined, and fundamental ideas are chosen. The general object of research, the search for its meaning, the need to search for new methods and types of activity can be the basis of an heuristic situation.

Disclosure of the essence of modern education, comprehensive coverage of pedagogical activity. Professional skills in future teachers and a creative approach to the lesson, the application of methods of a new form of teaching in it. Education is a collaborative activity of the teacher and students, in this process the development of the individual, his education and upbringing also take place. In classes, the teacher transmits his knowledge, skills and abilities to students through training, while students acquire the ability to use it as a result of mastering it. In the process of learning, students use different manifestations of assimilation, that is, they rely on specific differences in the reception, processing and application of the information being mastered. In the process of education, issues of cooperation of the teacher and students during the lesson, independent work of students, education and upbringing in the form of extracurricular activities are resolved.

The requirements of society are taken into account when defining education's goals. As a result, the educational objective should be suitable and balanced. In the scientific literature, it is emphasized that the formation of skills and abilities, the development of logical and creative thinking, increasing communicative literacy, instilling a national idea, the formation of Oriental Education, and the spiritual enrichment of the individual comprise the correct, clear, and appropriate use of the possibilities of the purpose of education. According to the educational objective, raising students' levels of autonomous thought, oral and written literacy, and logical development improves the culture of their communication. And on the basis of the educational goal, spiritual, ideological, refined upbringing is given. In the process of language learning, it becomes possible to bring closer to the cultural and moral values of the people.

As long as one of the wise men advised, "If you live in fear of the future, give your children good knowledge and encourage them to read." It would not be incorrect to state that the reforms implemented in our nation's education and educational system were not a project intended to produce results in a two-year or brief period in the true sense, but rather a shift that would have been felt for several hundred years. The idea that all the children of our country—my children—should be stronger, more educated, and undoubtedly happier than we are, is supported by a thoughtful politics that displays concern for the future of our president and our generation. It is known that the implementation of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of training, but also plays an important role in the

education of an independent and logical thinking, comprehensively harmonious highly spiritual person through the application of achievements of Science in practice.

In the development of creative activity, the use of forms and techniques for the formation of creative abilities, the organization of scientific activity on knowledge, which leads to scientific and creative research, has borne fruit. In this regard, the lessons of the development of creative activity were most effective, such as dialogue-lessons discussion, discussion, conversations, fantasy, research lessons, lessons of problem-making and solving; participatory lessons, modeling, artistic technical creativity, creativity, creation of small discoveries, writing essays, drawing up Chronicles, use of business Games, innovative techniques. It is held during a certain period of training as Game methods of lesson forms in the educational process. It is up to them to choose what technology the teacher and the student choose in achieving the result from the goal, since the main goal of both methods is clear: it is aimed at achieving the result, at which the student-student level of Knowledge, Group character, technology used depending on the circumstances are selected.

For example, to achieve the result, it is necessary to work with a computer, maybe a film, handouts, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology will be needed, which depends on the teacher and the student-student. At the same time, it is necessary to design the teaching process in advance, in the process the teacher must take into account the specific theme of the educational subject, the place and conditions, the TSO, the main thing is that the student is able to organize the possibility and need, as well as joint activities, only then the desired guaranteed result can be achieved. In short, the student must take the student to the center of Education. It is necessary for the teacher to design the process of the upcoming lesson in order to be able to see each lesson in a holistic way and visualize it. It is of great importance for the teacher to draw up a technological map of the upcoming lesson by him. Because the technological map of the lesson is drawn up on the basis of each subject, the subject being studied for each lesson, the nature of the subject, the possibility and extirrance of the students.

A lesson in which he can approach, understand science, its subject in a holistic way, spread it from the beginning, goal of the holistic educational process, and achieve the result is provided to him by a technological card, as above, compiled by the teacher on each subject of the discipline he is studying, on each lesson session. A technological card reader pupil is particularly likely to be brought to the center of education as a person, with its structure depending on necessity. This makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of training. In the process of teaching, the student is considered as a person, the use of various pedagogical technologies and modern techniques makes them independent, free thinking, search, creative approach to each issue, sense of responsibility, carry out scientific research work, analyze the interests of scientific literature in unimitable use, most importantly, in reading, science, pedogogka and the profession of his choice.

Achieving such a result requires the use of innovative and information technologies in the educational process in practice. They are very diverse. We will dwell on some of them and give an application regarding the procedure for their transfer. Modern methods presented in this methodological manual, or technological trainings that help to increase the effectiveness of teaching, contribute to the formation of logical, mental, creative, critical, independent thinking in student students, the development of their abilities, the upbringing of professional qualities necessary for hamdamutakhassis to become a competitive, mature specialist. We will develop the

creative activity of students using the techniques that can be used in the teaching process below. They're going to make a quick and easy creative theme come down quickly and easily.

The method of "networks" is aimed at teaching the student logical thinking, expanding the general sphere of thought, independently using literature. The method "3x4" is aimed at the fact that the student can freely think of students, give various ideas in a wide range, be able to analyze and draw conclusions in a single, small group in the educational process, give a definition. In primary education, the game is a form of creative activity. On the basis of knowledge and understanding of the social and material being, emotional - emotional, intellectual-moral develops. A number of research works have been carried out in psychology, ethnography, culture, pedagogy on games, their role in human development. At the end of the XIX century, the German scientist K. While Gross tried to systematically study games, the German psychologist K. Büller researches games as a "satisfying" activity. L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontyevs believe that if they connected and studied games with a theoretical focus on certain activities by the nature of the social, then D.B. Elkonin characterizes the management of personality behavior as a content and interprets it as an improving activity. But the only and most important main feature of the game is its ease in education.

In games, the child's behavior is formed and socialized freely. The most important aspect of the Games is its two-tone character, and its compatibility with dramatic art as well. In one case, the participants of the game perform a real activity associated with certain non-standard tasks in increasing it, and in the second case, the Games also acquire a conditional feature that deviates from real situations, feeling responsibility in most moments of this activity. Hence, the fact that games perform a two-way task causes it to have a developing result. Game activity glue is widely used in the educational process. These are business Games, didactic games, role-playing games, computer games.

Business games are a form of re-creation of the subject or social content of professional activity, modeling a system of relations characteristic of this type of practice. Ishbop consists in the development of the activities of its participants in the conduct of games in a special (game-style) imitation model. According to the character of the games, the games of the educational process are divided into research Games, the type of games on management and attestation. Games on the educational process create conditions for the correct Organization of professional activities in the perspective on educational subjects and the purposeful formation of a person. New knowledge acquired as a result of these conditions will help to correctly establish future professional activities. As you know, education is based on cooperation and acquires a collective character; it takes place in accordance with the rules of activity specific to the profession and the social rules of the team. In this sense, the didactic and educational significance of education is combined among themselves, increasing the activity of students in the form of gaming activities. The proposed problematic task in business Games stimulates participants on the basis of purposeful dialogical communication, increases their interests, an emotional spirit appears.

S. French means "5 rows". Sinkwein is a non-rhymed poem that helps to synthesize information (bring it into a single whole), in which information about the studied concept (phenomenon, event, topic) is collected, expressed by the word reader in different options and through different points of view. Sinkwain structuring is a complex idea, a skill that is important for expressing intuition and emotions in a few words. Dividing into clusters is a pedagogical strategy that helps students think about each subject in a free and open way. This

method develops the skills of establishing a connection between the concepts (phenomenon, event) under study of multi-variant thinking. The word "cluster" means a worm. Separation into clusters can be applied to encourage fixation in the phases of encouragement, awareness, and reflection. It is basically a strategy to evoke new thoughts, to reach existing knowledge, and to encourage a new way of thinking on a specific topic.

In conclusion, games are the main type of activity of children, through which students of junior school age learn and adapt to life, being, surroundings. In order to prepare for the effective organization of reading lessons in the elementary school, classes in reading lessons can be organized in independent methods of work and research, in the method of brainstorming. In this case, it will be of fundamental importance to allow students to learn by reading the artistic characteristics characteristic of such literary genres as a story, fairy tale, poem, parable, which are taught at school, to be able to independently analyze the work, to master its content and Idea, to master the skills of reading, the culture of speech. It is advisable to use the creation of clusters before the perfect study of a new topic. The Insert method is a means of tracking understanding. The Insert is a powerful tool that gives students the opportunity to actively monitor their perception in the learning process, since there is such a holler that a person may not be able to read the text to the end and remember what was written there. This is an example of cases when a person does not understand what he is reading, does not participate in the process of reading to be active and does not observe his own understanding. Insert is a powerful tool to support activity when working with text..

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